

MAGNETIC STUDY OF COLOUR CHANGES IN COPPER CHLORIDE

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Changes in magnetic susceptibility of cupric chloride in aqueous and hydrochloric acid solutions have been studied with change of temperature (35°, 55° and 75°) and with change of Cl⁻ ions keeping the concentration nearly constant with respect to CuCl₂.

It is well known that cupric chloride changes colour from green to blue when a concentrated solution is diluted. There are many explanations for this colour change which we have given briefly in our first communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 357). The more plausible of these explanations are due to

(a) Ostwald ("Grundlinien der anorganischen Chemie", Leipzig, 1900) who explains it on the basis of ionisation of molecules, suggesting that cupric ions are blue and CuCl₂ molecules are brown in colour. $\text{CuCl}_2 \text{ (brown)} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{2+} \text{ (blue)} + 2\text{Cl}^- \text{ (colourless)}$.

(b) Wiedemanns (*British Assoc. Rep.*, 1887, 346,) who attributes the colour change to solution of the solute. $\text{CuCl}_2 \text{ (brown)} + n \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CuCl}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O} \text{ (blue)}$.

(c) Donnan and Bassett (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 939) who attribute the colour change to the formation and dissociation of complex ions. $\text{CuCl}_2 \text{ (brown)} \rightarrow \text{CuCl}_4^{2-} \text{ (blue)} + 2\text{Cl}^-$.

In a previous communication (*loc. cit.*) we have shown that the magnetic susceptibility measurements are in favour of complex ion formation. Change of colour of the solution with change in temperature has also been noted and it has been found that the change is parallel to the change in concentration. This effect was first studied by Coppet (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1871, iv, 23, 386) who showed that blue colour changed to bluish green and then to green at higher temperatures.

Here again the same views are put forward and are supported by various workers and are briefly given below.

The hydration theory of Ostwald is supported by Lewis (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 56, 223; 1905, 52, 222), and Blitz (*ibid.*, 1902, 40, 199), who showed that a rise of temperature should cause dissociation of the hydrated ion into a less hydrated or non-hydrated ion.

Hartley and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 82, 401) from absorption band spectrum have shown that rise in temperature produces the same effect as an increased concentration. If the observed change were due to the formation of complexes between the solute and the solvent this would not be the case; as a change produced by rise in temperature on such complexes is just opposite to that produced by an increase in ion concentration.

Complex ion theory of Donnan and Basset is supported by Watkins and Denham (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 118, 1269), who have shown that decrease in transport number with rise of temperature favours the complex ion theory. Jones and Anderson ("Absorption Spectra of Solutions", Washington, 1909) also supported the same explanation. Bhagwat (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 53) also supports the complex ion theory.

If complex ion formation were the real cause of colour change, the addition of Cl⁻ ions to the solution would certainly favour the colour change. In this work we have studied the change of magnetic susceptibility with change of temperature, and with change of concentration of Cl⁻ ions in solution keeping the concentration with respect to CuCl₂ nearly constant.

To increase the concentration of Cl^- ions various concentrations of hydrochloric acid were employed and the different temperatures used were 35° , 55° and 75° .

EXPERIMENTAL

Two solutions of $CuCl_2$ were prepared, one in water and the second in HCl and the concentration of $CuCl_2$ was kept the same in both i.e., about 5%. Colour in HCl solution was green and in aqueous solutions it was blue. Different proportions of these solutions were mixed to give different strengths of HCl but the strength of $CuCl_2$ remained the same in all the solutions. In these solutions there was a colour change. This could only be due to changing strength of HCl in solution or concentration of HCl .

The susceptibility measurements were made on a modified form of Guoy's balance. To maintain various temperatures a silica tube, wound round with a heating coil, was used.

In the case of the solutions the susceptibilities have been calculated on the assumption that the magnetic susceptibility of the solution is equal to the sum of component susceptibilities.

$$\chi_s = \frac{\chi_{sol} - \chi_v(1 - C_s)}{C_s}$$

Where χ_s , χ_v and χ_{sol} are magnetic susceptibilities of solute, solvent and solution, C_s is the amount of solute in 1g. of the solution.

Magnetic susceptibility of the conductivity water which was used in the present work was -0.720×10^{-6} .

Cupric chloride (Merck's guaranteed reagent) was dehydrated according to the method of Sabatier (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1889, iii, 1, 88). Its susceptibility was found out at 35° , 55° and 75° to be 8.718×10^{-6} , 8.204×10^{-6} and 7.725×10^{-6} respectively.

Hydrochloric acid, which was used in this work had susceptibility -0.661×10^{-6} at all these temperatures

TABLE I

Influence of HCl on the magnetic susceptibility of aq. soln. of $CuCl_2$

%Composition of the soln. by wt.	Normality of the acid in soln.	χ soln. $\times 10^6$ at 35° .		Colour.	χ soln. $\times 10^6$ at 55° .		Colour.	χ soln. $\times 10^6$ at 75° .		Colour.
		Obs.	Calc.		Obs.	Calc.		Obs.	Calc.	
$CuCl_2$, HCl, H_2O .										
4.20 30.68 65.12	8.400	-0.219	-0.305	Green.	—	—	Green	—	—	Green
4.30 25.13 70.57	6.885	-0.225	-0.299		-0.240	-0.321		-0.301	0.342	
4.41 19.33 76.26	5.296	-0.222	-0.292		-0.248	-0.321		-0.300	0.335	
4.54 13.25 82.21	3.630	-0.218	-0.284		-0.245	-0.307		-0.298	0.329	
4.66 6.81 88.53	1.874	-0.189	-0.276	-0.244	-0.300	-0.296	0.322			
4.73 3.45 91.82	0.245	-0.188	-0.271	-0.234	-0.296	-0.298	0.318			
4.80 0.00 95.20	—	-0.187	-0.266	-0.233	-0.292	-0.294	0.314			

An examination of the table shows that until the concentration of HCl in the solution is 13.25% i.e., corresponding to 4N-HCl there is a small regular increase in the difference between the observed and calculated susceptibility of solution. On further decrease in the concentration of HCl, the solution turns from green to blue and a new magnetic carrier ion is formed. The difference is great as compared to the previous readings which show the formation of a more paramagnetic ion. On plotting the graph we find that there is a break in the curve and the two parts of the curve correspond to two different colours exactly. There is a big gap in the susceptibility of the solutions in two parts showing sudden change in the composition of the solution. This sudden break can only be due to the formation of a new compound.

The theories of hydration and ionisation are ruled out on the basis of the work of previous workers and especially of Datta (*Phil. Mag.*, 1934, 16, 585) who have shown that hydration cannot bring a change in magnetic moment and as long as ions in solution remain the same magnetic moment does not change also.

Table I also shows the effects of change of temperature. The solutions (5th and 6th), which are blue at 35°, gradually change to the green form and at 75° even the 7th solution is green.

This shows that rise in temperature brings about exactly the same change as is brought about either by increase in concentration of CuCl₂ or of Cl⁻ by the addition of HCl. This is in favour of the work of Coppet (*loc. cit.*).

FIG. 1.

It has been shown by Jones and West also from the study of temperature coefficient that if the increase in concentration and rise in temperature produce the same effect it is due to the formation of complex ions of the type CuCl_2 and CuCl_4 . Same results have been obtained by Bhagwat by studying the application of Beer's law.

We have not taken into account the small change in concentration of CuCl_2 in plotting these curves and the same is the case in curve III (75°) which is absolutely a straight line. Had there been no colour change and no formation of new magnetic carriers, the other two curves would have been straight lines. The splitting up of first two curves into two different parts is simply due to the formation of new carrier ions which are more paramagnetic.

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